

The Precursors of Transit-oriented Development

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Transit-oriented development has emerged as a promising urban planning approach to address the challenges of urbanisation, congestion, and sustainability. The importance of transportation infrastructure, land-use policies, economic incentives, community engagement, and regulatory frameworks are essential precursors to fostering TOD. The interplay between these precursors is explored in various urban contexts, revealing the complex and context-sensitive nature of TOD implementation.

In the face of rapid urbanisation, escalating congestion, and the pressing need for sustainable urban development, the concept of transit-oriented development (TOD) has emerged as a pivotal paradigm for shaping modern cities (Ibraeva et al 2020). The inherent potential of TOD to foster efficient transportation systems, encourage compact urban growth, and promote environmentally conscious living has spurred its widespread adoption by planners, policymakers, and urban designers (Litman 2002). However, while the benefits of TOD are well-documented, its successful implementation remains contingent on an array of precursors that collectively determines its viability and efficacy within a given urban context.

Discussions revolving around urban transportation frequently generate more passionate opinions than constructive insights. To begin with, an ongoing debate revolves around the interplay between highways and public transit systems. Public transit advocates have often been criticised for making exaggerated claims about the myriad environmental and societal benefits stemming from investing in transit infrastructure. What often goes unnoticed in this discourse is the fact that transit serves as a specialised tool, and the transition towards more compact, transit-centric urban planning is inherently gradual, given the overwhelming prevalence of automobiles and highways in modern society. Conversely, proponents of highways and automobiles tend to criticise public transit based on national statistics and regional averages without acknowledging that public transit primarily caters to urban environments. Public transit thrives as a component of a comprehensive strategy that intertwines transit, urban development, and complementary policies (Badoo and Miller 2000). Another prominent debate pits libertarians against proponents of smart growth in the context of land use. Libertarians argue that existing urban

growth patterns reflect market demands, dismissing the decades of government influence in urban planning and the substantial government funding directed towards highways and cars. Residential density plays an important role in promoting and adopting the TOD-based development in many cities (Cervero and Kockelman 1997).

Moreover, smart growth advocates tend to exaggerate the effectiveness of planning interventions and disregard the persistent appeal of detached single-family residences in suburban areas with quality educational institutions. Additionally, they might overlook the considerable challenge of altering deeply entrenched lifestyles and habits. Amid these debates, the concept of TOD has emerged as a potential panacea (Dittmar and Ohland 2012). Some proponents contend that urban expansion can be effectively accommodated through denser infill development along transit corridors. While this is physically plausible, it might encounter limitations within a democratic society with varying interests and perspectives. These debates underscore the complexity of harmonising transportation and urban planning. They highlight the need for a nuanced understanding that acknowledges both the benefits and limitations of transit, highways, land-use policies, and entrenched societal preferences.

Constructing a well-rounded approach necessitates a recognition of the multifaceted nature of urban development and the intricate interplay between transportation strategies and the social fabric of communities (Sallis et al 2015). The essence of TOD lies in its emphasis on strategically integrating land use and transportation infrastructure, thereby facilitating a shift towards less car-dependent urban lifestyles (Pojani and Stead 2014). By fostering mixed-use developments around transit nodes and corridors, TOD creates vibrant, pedestrian-friendly urban spaces that reduce congestion and pollution and enhance residents' quality of life. Yet, the realisation of these goals is fundamentally intertwined with the presence and interaction of several precursors, encompassing a spectrum of factors that shape the feasibility and outcome of TOD initiatives.

This article delves into the intricate web of precursors that underpins the successful

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implementation of TOD. Through an exploration of existing literature and empirical evidence, this study sheds light on the multifaceted nature of these precursors and the intricate interplay between them. By dissecting the key elements that pave the way for effective TOD projects, this article seeks to provide a comprehensive framework that assists urban planners, policy-makers, and stakeholders in navigating the complexities of TOD implementation. As cities worldwide strive to grapple with the urbanisation's challenges, this investigation into the precursors of TOD contributes to the broader dialogue on sustainable urban development and offers insights that are poised to shape the future urban landscape.

The precursors are the foundational elements and factors that contribute to the successful planning, design, and implementation of TOD projects. These precursors are essential in shaping TOD initiatives' feasibility, effectiveness, and sustainability. While the specific precursors can vary based on local contexts, some common factors are listed below.

Proximity to transit infrastructure: The availability and accessibility of existing or planned transit infrastructure, such as bus stops, train stations, and light rail systems are fundamental to TOD. The proximity of development to these transportation nodes allows for seamless connectivity and encourages transit ridership (Nyunt and Wongchavalidkul 2020).

Mixed-use zoning and land-use policies: TOD thrives on the integration of various land uses, including residential, commercial,

office, and recreational spaces. Zoning regulations and land-use policies that encourage mixed-use developments and higher densities around transit corridors are crucial for fostering vibrant and walkable neighbourhoods.

Compact urban design: The physical layout of the development, characterised by higher densities and compact building arrangements, encourages efficient land use. This design approach minimises sprawl and promotes pedestrian-friendly environments (Furlan et al 2019).

Walkability and pedestrian infrastructure: The presence of safe and well-designed pedestrian infrastructure such as sidewalks, crosswalks, and pedestrian plazas, supports the walkability aspect of TOD. Walkable neighbourhoods are conducive to reducing car dependency and promoting active transportation (Rafiemanzelat et al 2017).

Bicycle infrastructure: Including bike lanes, bike-sharing programmes, and secure bike storage encourages cycling as an alternative mode of transportation, further reducing reliance on cars.

Transit integration: Beyond physical proximity, effective integration of transit systems with the surrounding development is vital. This includes factors like convenient access points, clear way finding, and synchronised schedules.

Affordable housing: Ensuring a mix of housing options, including affordable

housing units, within TOD projects promotes social inclusivity and enables a diverse range of residents to benefit from improved transit connectivity (Thomas and Bertolini 2020).

Public spaces and amenities: Designing public spaces, parks, and recreational facilities within the TOD area enhances the overall quality of life for residents, making the neighbourhood more attractive and liveable (Safaei et al 2016).

Methodology

A systematic literature review (SLR) is a methodical and comprehensive approach for analysing existing literature on a specific topic, aiming to synthesise and evaluate relevant studies to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject (Dehalwar and Sharma 2023). The research methodology employed for the SLR on the topic of "Precursor of TOD" involved a multistep approach to refine and select relevant scholarly papers.

Initially, a broad search using the term "Precursor of TOD" yielded 29,627 results, which were subsequently narrowed down by filtering papers published between 2019 and 2023, resulting in 16,940 papers. Further refinement involved filtering based on research papers, which reduced the selection to 11,824 papers. Subsequently, screening based on open access availability was conducted, leading to 2,885 accessible papers. The process continued with a meticulous examination of abstracts, resulting in the selection of 174 papers deemed relevant to the research topic. Finally, 51 papers were chosen for detailed study based on their perceived relevance and potential contribution to the research objectives (Figure 1). This systematic methodology ensures that the final selection of papers is rigorous and aligned with the scope of the study on TOD precursors.

This article employs a qualitative research approach, utilising historical documents, scholarly articles, government reports, and urban planning literature to analyse the precursors for TOD in the selected megaprojects. By applying a comparative analysis, the study identifies commonalities and unique factors that influenced the adoption of TOD principles.

Figure 1: Systematic Literature Review of TOD

Source: Authors' compilation.

Findings and Discussion

The study on the precursors of TOD reveals several important findings.

TOD effects: A considerable volume of research endeavours has been dedicated to examining TOD impacts (Xia and Zhang 2022). Through an analysis of the existing body of literature, we have categorised this research into five distinct domains based on the nature of the effects investigated. Each of these domains is presented in separate subcategories below. The realm of the study that has received the most attention pertains to the alterations in travel behaviour (particularly the selection of transportation modes, as anticipated, along with trip generation and parking considerations). Subsequently, there has been a significant focus on comprehending the repercussions on real estate values within and around TOD locales. Additional impacts, although less extensively scrutinised, encompass those relating to residential location (exhibiting a bidirectional relationship—evaluating the influence of travel behaviour on individuals’ residential choices and vice versa), urban morphology (pertaining to effects on land utilisation, spatial arrangement, and accessibility of activities), and community dynamics (Ibraeva et al 2020).

In Figure 2, the dimensions of the squares correspond proportionally to the number of scholarly articles that tackle various forms of effects. It is worth noting that certain articles address more than one effect simultaneously (for instance, both travel behaviour and residential location). This multifaceted approach is depicted in Figure 2 by arrows with their widths denoting the number of articles that delve into at least two distinct types of effects concurrently.

Transition from TAD to TOD: One of the pivotal attributes of TOD lies in its propensity to serve as an acceptable setting for elevated-density development within suburban locales (Figure 3). A seminal work by Newman and Kenworthy (1999) underscores this aspect, proposing a critical guideline. They advocate that achieving a density of at least 35 individuals and job opportunities per hectare

Figure 2: TOD Effects and Their Interactions

Source: Ibraeva et al (2020).

is imperative for developing an urban landscape that effectively mitigates automobile reliance (Newman and Kenworthy 1999). Below this threshold, the resulting urban configuration lacks the requisite density to fully harness the advantages of an urban layout oriented towards pedestrian mobility, cycling, and public transit. Consequently, it becomes evident that, within a radius of approximately a 10-minute walk from a transit station, the vicinity should be designed to accommodate no fewer than 10,000 residents and employment opportunities (Newman and Kenworthy 1999).

This recommendation underscores the significance of compact and concentrated development around transit nodes to foster sustainable transportation practices. It signifies the need to congregate populations and activities in close proximity to public transit, allowing for a seamless integration of various transportation modes. This approach not only diminishes the necessity for private vehicle usage but also fosters vibrant and accessible

urban environments that promote active mobility. By adhering to these density principles, TOD can potentially balance living spaces and workplaces, supporting diverse activities, and encouraging sustainable transportation options. However, it is important to note that the successful implementation of such density requirements necessitates careful urban planning, zoning regulations, and the creation of mixed-use environments that cater to the needs and preferences of the local population (Renne 2009).

Holistic approach: TOD success is contingent on a combination of factors rather than any one isolated precursor. The synergy between factors like transit access, zoning policies, and community engagement creates a robust foundation for sustainable urban growth.

Interdependence: The precursors of TOD are interconnected. For instance, effective zoning regulations enable mixed-use development, which in turn supports higher population density and a diverse range of housing options. This interdependence underscores the need for comprehensive urban planning.

Economic and environmental benefits: TOD should incorporate the identified precursors, which can yield economic benefits through increased property values, reduced traffic congestion, and improved air quality. Additionally, these developments contribute to reduced greenhouse gas emissions by promoting public transportation and active mobility.

Challenges: Implementing TOD precursors requires overcoming challenges such

Figure 3: Transit Adjacent Development (TAD) to Transit-oriented Development (TOD)

TAD ←=====→ TOD	
• Suburban street pattern	• Grid street pattern
• Low densities	• High densities
• Dominance of surface parking	• Mostly underground or structured parking
• Limited or no pedestrian access	• Pedestrian-focused design, bicycle access/parking
• Single family homes/single- or double-storey buildings	• Multifamily homes/multistorey buildings
• Industrial land uses	• Office and retail land uses
• Segregated land uses	• Vertically and horizontally mixed land uses
• Gas stations, car dealerships, drive-through stores and other auto-focused land uses	• Predominance of service-based industries and corporate offices

Source: Renne (2009).

as resistance to change, inadequate infrastructure, and potential gentrification. Addressing these challenges necessitates careful planning, continuous community engagement, and adaptive policies.

Adaptability to context: While certain precursors like transit accessibility and mixed land use are universal, the specific implementation of TOD precursors can vary based on the local context, culture, and existing urban fabric.

TOD is a planning strategy that aims to create compact, mixed-use, and walkable communities centred around public transportation hubs. The success of TOD depends on a multitude of factors, and understanding its precursors is crucial for effective urban development. This discussion delves into the key precursors of TOD and their significance in shaping sustainable urban environments.

Proximity to public transit infrastructure: One of the fundamental precursors of TOD is the availability and accessibility of well-developed public transportation systems, such as subways, buses, and light rail (Cervero and Murakami 2009). A TOD's success hinges on the convenience of transit services for residents, encouraging them to rely less on personal vehicles and reducing traffic congestion.

Zoning and land-use policies: Supportive zoning regulations that permit mixed-use development (residential, commercial, and recreational) around transit nodes are essential. These policies encourage high-density, diverse, and pedestrian-friendly neighbourhoods, fostering a vibrant urban fabric (Hughen and Read 2017).

Density and building design: High population density around transit hubs is a hallmark of TOD. Increased density ensures efficient land use and maximises the number of people within walking distance of transit options. Proper building design, such as creating pedestrian pathways and open spaces and reducing parking space, further enhances the attractiveness of using public transportation (Knowles et al 2020).

Affordability and housing options: TODs should cater to a diverse socio-economic

Figure 4: Conceptual Plan for Developing TOD-based High-rise DDA Flats in New Delhi

Source: Roy (2014).

population. Integrating affordable housing options near transit nodes can help mitigate the displacement of lower-income residents due to rising property values in these areas.

Community engagement: Successful TOD initiatives require community involvement in the planning process. Engaging residents and stakeholders fosters a sense of ownership and ensures that the development aligns with local needs, preferences, and cultural characteristics.

Pedestrian and cyclist infrastructure: Safe and well-designed pedestrian and cyclist infrastructure is critical for encouraging active transportation modes. Sidewalks, bike lanes, and pedestrian crossings make walking and cycling viable options for short trips within the TOD area.

New Delhi—A TOD-based Development

TOD is a promising urban planning approach that creates vibrant, sustainable, and livable communities centred around efficient public transportation systems. One notable case study that exemplifies the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing TOD principles is the capital city of India, New Delhi (Figure 4).

The context: New Delhi has for long grappled with issues like traffic congestion, air pollution, and inadequate public transportation. As the city's population continues to grow, the need for innovative

urban planning solutions has become urgent. TOD presents itself as a potential remedy, aligning with New Delhi's aspirations for improved mobility, reduced environmental impact, and enhanced quality of life for its residents.

Expansion of the Delhi Metro: The Delhi Metro serves as a cornerstone of the city's transit infrastructure. Its rapid expansion, spanning various phases, has significantly improved connectivity and accessibility. The metro system has become a catalyst for TOD, influencing land-use patterns and development around its stations (Phani Kumar et al 2020).

TOD requires seamless integration between different modes of transportation. In New Delhi, efforts have been made to link the metro with other transport options like buses, cycle-sharing, and pedestrian pathways. This multimodal approach enhances the viability of TOD by providing commuters with various choices for their daily travels.

Zonal plans and land use: The city's Master Plan and Zonal Development Plans play a pivotal role in shaping urban growth. Introducing TOD-oriented land-use policies in these plans encourages higher density development near transit nodes, fostering mixed-use neighbourhoods that reduce the need for long commutes (Raman and Roy 2019).

Affordable housing initiatives: TOD seeks to provide accessible housing options

close to transit hubs. In New Delhi, projects like the Delhi Development Authority's Land Pooling Policy aim to create affordable housing within TOD zones, catering to diverse income groups and reducing urban sprawl.

Policy and regulatory support: New Delhi's policies have been increasingly geared towards TOD implementation. This includes floor area ratio bonuses for developers near transit nodes, incentivising them to create denser, more walkable neighbourhoods (Rangwala et al 2014).

Public engagement: The success of TOD depends on the involvement of local communities. New Delhi has witnessed public engagement efforts in planning processes, allowing citizens to voice their preferences and needs, ultimately shaping the development of transit-oriented neighbourhoods that resonate with their aspirations.

Challenges and Future Directions

While New Delhi has made big strides in adopting TOD principles, challenges remain. Coordinating the efforts of various stakeholders, managing population density, ensuring equitable access, and addressing resistance to change are ongoing tasks. As New Delhi continues to evolve, the integration of sustainable transport with land-use planning remains a challenge.

The case study of New Delhi highlights the complex interplay between transportation, urban planning, and community engagement in the pursuit of TOD. By leveraging existing transit assets, aligning policies, and engaging citizens, Delhi's journey towards TOD serves as a valuable lesson for cities worldwide striving to create a more sustainable, inclusive, and connected urban environment.

Conclusions

The precursors for TOD lay the groundwork for creating sustainable, livable, and inclusive urban communities. A holistic approach that considers factors ranging from transportation infrastructure to community engagement is crucial for successful TOD implementation. Understanding these precursors aids urban planners, policymakers, and stakeholders in designing cities that prioritise public transportation,

reduce congestion, and enhance overall quality of life.

In sum, it stands to reason that, as a broad trend, being in close proximity to a station that embodies TOD attributes—such as high population density, mixed land usage, and pedestrian-friendly infrastructure—contributes to an increase in the utilisation of public transportation. Simultaneously, this proximity also leads to a rise in property values within the surrounding regions. Consequently, this surge in property prices has the potential to set in motion a spate of events, possibly resulting in the gradual intensification of development and, in some cases, the transformation of the station areas through processes like gentrification.

However, there arises a question regarding the sustainability of elevated public transport ridership levels once more affluent segments of the population establish residence within TOD zones. This is subject to debate as the influx of higher-income groups might alter the socio-economic composition of these areas and potentially impact travel behaviour patterns. It is important to note that these changes typically unfold gradually over time, suggesting that certain effects associated with TOD might require a certain period to become fully evident. The evolution of transit utilisation, property values, and urban transformation in TOD regions is not an immediate occurrence but a progressive development. This investigation highlights the intricate interplay between TOD, transportation behaviour, and urban dynamics. The findings underscore the potential benefits of TOD in promoting sustainable transportation and urban development, while also acknowledging the complex and multifaceted nature of the changes that unfold in these areas over time.

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